

SOSCHI

Standards for Official Statistics on
Climate-Health Interactions

Mental health outcomes relating to climate-sensitive extreme weather events: A scoping review of measures of mental health impact

Publication date: 15 May 2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20085842>

Status: This scoping review has been submitted to a journal for peer review

In partnership with:

Cochrane
Planetary Health

Funded by Wellcome grant no. 224682/Z/21/Z

Document information

Document title Mental health outcomes relating to climate-sensitive extreme weather events: A scoping review of measures of mental health impact

Document location Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/soschi>

Date and version 15 May 2026 (preprint version)

Authors

- Thomson Denise^{a,c} dthomson@ualberta.ca
- Sebastianski Meghan^{b,c} meghan.sebastianski@gmail.com
- O’Hearn Katie^b kohearn@cheo.on.ca
- Nuspl Megan^{b,c} msommerv@ualberta.ca
- Bobier Sol^{b,c} sol.bobier@gmail.com
- Abdul Sami Aftab^b SAbdul@cheo.on.ca
- Pearce Matt^d matthew.pearce@ons.gov.uk
- Ingole Vijendra^d vijendra.ingole@ons.gov.uk
- Glickman Myer^d myer.glickman@ons.gov.uk
- Webster Richard J^{b,c,e} rwebster@cheo.on.ca

a. University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada

b. CHEO Research Institute, Ottawa, Canada

c. Cochrane Planetary Health Thematic Group, London, United Kingdom

d. Climate and Health Team, Office for National Statistics (ONS), Newport, United Kingdom

e. Telfer School of Management, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

Author contributions

Conceptualization: DT, MS, MP, VI, MG and RW. Supervision: DT and RW. Project administration: DT, MS, KO, RW. Data curation (screening, data extraction): MS, MN and SB. Visualization and data presentation: MS, MN, SB and SA. Writing, original draft: DT, MS, MN, KO, RW. Writing, review and editing: DT, MS, MP, VI,

	<p>MG and RW. Funding acquisition: MG. Formal analysis: All authors participated in interpreting the results. All authors had full access to all the data in the study and had final responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.</p>
Corresponding author address and email	<p>Richard Webster, CHEO, Clinical Research Unit, 401 Smyth Road, Ottawa, Canada, K1H 8L1 rwebster@cheo.on.ca</p>
DOI	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20085842</p>
Preferred citation	<p>Thomson D, Sebastianski M, O'Hearn K, Nuspl M, Bobier S, Abdul SA, et al. Mental health outcomes relating to climate-sensitive extreme weather events: A scoping review of measures of mental health impact. Zenodo; 2026.doi:10.5281/zenodo.20085842</p>
Word Count	<p>3,346</p>
Accompanying documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Figures 1 to 4 (see section 6 for figure legends)• Tables 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria• Table 2: Summary of EWEs and frequency of most common mental health outcomes• Table 3: Summary of most common mental health outcomes and type and frequency of measures of mental health impact• Supplementary Material 1: Search Strategy• Supplementary Material 2: Table S1. Characteristics of included studies• Supplementary Material 3: Table S2. Categorization based on the groupings of mental health impact by mental health outcome• Supplementary Material 4: Table S3. Frequency of mental health outcome measures for type of extreme weather event
Related Documents	<p>Standards for Official Statistics on Climate-Health Interactions (SOSCHI): Extreme weather events due to</p>

climate change and mental health outcome indicators: a scoping review protocol. ([10.5281/zenodo.15374227](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15374227))

Declaration of interest We declare no competing interests

Copyright This is an open access document published under a UK [Open Government Licence 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) which is compatible with the Creative Commons [CC-BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) licence. You are free to copy, publish, distribute and adapt the information, provided you acknowledge the source and link to this publication or the ONS [SOSCHI project home page](#). Institutional logos are the property of the relevant institutions.

Acknowledgements The authors would like to thank Mr. D Salzwedel, MLIS, for development and execution of the search strategy. The authors would also like to thank Meg Schweltnus for her assistance preparing tables and figures. This publication has been produced by the Cochrane Planetary Health Thematic Group as part of the Standards for Official Statistics on Climate-Health Interactions (SOSCHI) project, led by the UK Office for National Statistics and funded by Wellcome. This research was funded by Wellcome (Grant number: 224682/Z/21/Z).

Abstract

Introduction:

Climate change is contributing to an increase in frequency and severity of extreme weather events (EWEs), which have a sizable impact on mental health and wellbeing. We sought to comprehensively synthesize mental health outcome measures used in the literature following EWEs.

Materials and Methods:

This scoping review searched eight databases from 2017 to September 2024 to identify primary research studies that measured and reported mental health outcomes following EWEs. We categorized findings to describe

- a) which EWEs were most heavily studied,
- b) which mental health outcomes appeared more or less frequently,
- c) which measures of mental health impact were employed, and
- d) evidence gaps.

Results:

We screened 3,689 studies and included 154 studies from 29 countries, 15 (51.7%) of which were low- and middle-income countries. Studies reporting mental health outcomes were most commonly investigating the impact of 11 types of EWEs. We identified 188 mental health outcomes and 130 measures of mental health impact. Mental health outcomes were most commonly evaluated in studies investigating the impact of floods ($n = 41$), extreme heat/heatwaves ($n = 32$) and wildfires ($n = 28$). The most frequently evaluated mental health outcomes were post-traumatic stress disorder ($n = 62$), depression ($n = 39$) and anxiety ($n = 27$). The most commonly used measure of mental health impact was International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) codes.

Conclusion:

The results of this review will contribute to the development of a transparent and globally usable framework for official statistics on climate and health.

Keywords:

Extreme weather events, climate change, mental health, mental health impact, mental health outcomes, official statistics

1. Introduction

Evidence is accumulating that climate change is increasing the intensity, frequency, duration, and seasonality of extreme weather events (EWEs) such as floods, extreme heat/heatwaves and wildfires.[1] These events have a range of adverse impacts on global mental health and wellbeing, both directly, e.g. exposure to flooding or wildfires, and/or indirectly, e.g. grief for the loss of traditional ways of life.[2] Further, there is a real risk that climate change may erode hope, which must be nurtured in order to support humanity's ability to meet this unprecedented challenge.[3] Researchers and policymakers urgently need high-quality, accessible and reliable evidence and data to support the development, implementation and sustainment of adequate policy responses.[4]

Recognizing the need to support decision-making for climate adaptation in health systems and better understanding of health outcomes, the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS), funded by Wellcome and in collaboration with the African Institute for Mathematical Sciences (AIMS) Rwanda, the Regional Institute for Population Studies (RIPS) at the University of Ghana, the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA), and the Cochrane Planetary Health Thematic Group (hosted at University of Alberta) has developed the Standards for Official Statistics on Climate-Health Interactions (SOSCHI) project.[5] The goal of SOSCHI is to develop a transparent, globally generalizable, and spatially scalable (from local to national) framework and technical platform for official statistics on climate and health. Substantial foundational work to understand current practice is required to achieve this goal. The purpose of this scoping review, which was led by the Cochrane Planetary Health Thematic Group (CPHTG), was to map currently available mental health outcomes and measures of mental health impact directly relevant to climate-sensitive EWEs. Due to operational requirements of the SOCHI project, climate-sensitive EWEs of interest were defined as low pressure systems (cyclone, hurricanes, tornadoes, typhoons), extreme heat (extreme heat and heat waves), extreme cold (extreme cold and cold spells), extreme precipitation (extreme rainfall and snowstorms), drought, floods, and wildfires.

2. Methods

We performed a scoping review following the framework of Arksey and O'Malley[6] as well as the PRISMA-ScR extension for scoping reviews.[7] The scoping review method supports exploratory work related to broad research questions and is therefore well-suited to the purpose of this study.[6] With previous work showing a large increase in the number of new publications on this topic appearing since 2017,[8] the author team agreed that focusing on studies from 2017 onwards would provide sufficient material to reach saturation. The protocol for this review was published on SOSCHI (Standards

for Official Statistics on Climate Health Interactions) Zenodo open repository (<https://zenodo.org/records/15374228>) on May 13, 2025.

2.1 Search Strategy and Selection Criteria

The search strategy for this scoping review (Supplementary Material 1) was developed by an information specialist in consultation with the author team. The search terms captured the concepts of the EWEs listed above, mental health outcomes and measures of mental health impact. We searched the following platforms and databases from 2017 to September 2024: Ovid MEDLINE ALL, Ovid Embase Classic+Embase, Ovid APA PsycInfo, Clarivate Web of Science's Science Citation Index and Emerging Sources Citation Index, Elsevier Scopus, EBSCO CABI Global Health, and Epistemonikos. Except for Epistemonikos (searched on September 29, 2024), all databases were searched on September 28, 2024. No limits were placed in the search on geographical location, language, or publication type.

All records returned through the electronic database search were screened independently at the title and abstract level by two reviewers using Covidence (<https://www.covidence.org/>). The full inclusion and exclusion criteria can be found in Table 1. Any records deemed potentially relevant were retrieved for further examination. Full text documents were further subjected to independent screening by two reviewers, and any uncertain judgements or disagreements were resolved by consensus discussions. All primary studies included at this stage were retained for data extraction. Relevant scoping and systematic reviews were retained for hand screening of their included studies. At all stages of screening, we piloted a subset of 20-30 studies to ensure consistency between reviewers.

2.2 Data Extraction

A data extraction template was developed in Excel (Microsoft) through consultation between the ONS and the CPHTG, and was piloted by the reviewers completing data extraction to ensure inter-reviewer consistency. Data was extracted by one reviewer and verified by a second. Any inconsistencies were noted and resolved by consensus discussions. Key information was extracted from each record, including authors or producing organization, year of publication, mental health outcomes presented and available details for any breakdown of data by demographic and social characteristics/intersectionality, and measures of mental health impact (e.g. International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes, standardized questionnaires, rating scales).

2.3 Analysis of Evidence

We categorized our findings to describe a) which of the included EWEs were the most heavily studied, b) which mental health outcomes appeared more or less frequently, c) which measures of mental health impact were employed, and d) where any evidence gaps existed. Countries were categorized as low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) using Wellcome's list of LMICs, which is based on a classification updated every three years by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD).[9]

2.4 Measures of Mental Health Impact and Mental Health Outcomes

Due to the operational requirements of the SOCHI project, we focused on studies reporting direct mental health outcomes from EWEs (e.g. anxiety, depression, PTSD, acute stress, suicidal behaviour, intentional self-harm, mood disorder, dementia, Alzheimer disease, schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders, acute and transient psychotic disorders, psychosis, substance use and addiction), and excluded studies reporting indirect outcomes (e.g. domestic abuse, general climate change anxiety, psychological and behavioural disorders associated with sexual development and orientation, disorders of psychological development). We sorted mental health outcomes into categories based on the groupings of diagnostic criteria and codes from the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5) and the International Classification of Diseases 10th and 11th revisions. For each mental health outcome, we categorized the measures of mental health impact used and how that data was collected at the study level. Measures of mental health impact included both primary sources such as symptom scales, screening tools, surveys and questionnaires, and secondary sources such as International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes which are recorded mainly in administrative data (hospital admissions, mortality, emergency room (ER) visits).

3. Results

The database search returned 2,921 unique records. An additional 1,009 records were identified from handsearching relevant systematic reviews before duplicates were removed. After duplicate removal, a total of 3,689 records were screened with 154 primary studies included in this scoping review (see Supplementary Material 2 for list of included studies and their characteristics). Figure 1 shows the flow of records through a PRISMA diagram. The 154 studies were conducted in 29 countries, 15 of which were LMIC (51.7%). Overall, 64 studies were conducted in LMICs, with a few

studies including multiple countries: China (n=21), India (n=13), Philippines (n=9), Bangladesh (n=5), Indonesia (n=5), Vietnam (n=3), Botswana (n=2), and 1 study each for Brazil, Burundi, Ethiopia, Ghana, Malaysia, Pakistan, South Africa and Thailand. Ninety-eight studies were conducted in high-income countries, again with a few studies including multiple countries: United States (n=37), Australia (n=20), Canada (n=14), United Kingdom (n=9), three studies each for Japan, South Korea and Spain, two studies each for Switzerland and Taiwan, and one study each for the Bahamas, Belgium, Finland, Greece and Sweden.

From the included studies, we identified 11 types of climate change-related EWEs for which the impacts on mental health were measured. Mental health outcomes were most often evaluated in studies investigating the impact of floods (41 studies), extreme heat / heat waves (32 studies), and wildfires (28 studies). Other types of EWEs studied in relation to mental health impacts were hurricanes (21 studies), droughts (12 studies), typhoons (9 studies), extreme cold / cold spells (6 studies), tornados (6 studies), cyclones (3 studies), extreme rainfalls (2 studies), and snowstorms (2 studies).

Overall, the studies evaluated 188 mental health outcomes which we classified into 17 DSM-5 categories (Figure 2) (see Supplementary Material 3 for summary of mental health outcomes within each DSM-5 category). Outcomes of Trauma and Stressor-Related Disorders had the highest diversity of mental health outcomes (n=43), followed by General Mental Health Outcomes (n=21), and Substance-Related and Addictive Disorders (n=21), while three categories had only one outcome (Bipolar, Neurodevelopmental, Obsessive-Compulsive and Related Disorders). Across these categories, the five most reported unique outcomes were post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (n=62), depression (n=39), anxiety (n=27), psychological distress (n=12) and suicidal ideation (n=12). The Sankey diagram in Figure 3 shows the links between EWEs and mental health outcome categories evaluated. Trauma- and stressor-related disorders were the most frequently evaluated category (n = 142), followed by depressive (n = 69) and anxiety disorders (n = 56). Studies focused on floods and wildfires evaluated the greatest number of mental health outcomes at 138 and 101 respectively. The most common mental health outcomes per EWE are reported in Table 2. A complete disaggregated list of mental health outcomes by EWE is available in Supplementary Material 4. Figure 4 shows the relationship between EWE and mental health outcomes, with bubble size indicating the frequency of reported outcomes and color intensity representing the number of unique measures of mental health impact used. Studies of floods and low-pressure systems most frequently evaluated trauma- and stressor-related disorders, while other outcomes like depressive and anxiety disorders were evaluated in studies focused across multiple EWE types. A gap analysis revealed that many of the mental health categories were not measured for all EWEs; 36% (33/91) of EWEs by mental health categories had a gap.

We identified a total of 130 measures of mental health impact. The most commonly used measure was ICD-10 codes with a frequency of 83 followed by the Patient Health Questionnaire - 9 (PHQ-9) (n=25), ICD-9 (n=21), Depression Anxiety and Stress Scales (DASS-21) (n=20), and the Post-traumatic Stress Disorder Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5) (n=17). ICD codes from the 8, 9 and 10th revisions were reported, with 67 mental health outcomes being reported by ICD codes. A summary of the five most common mental health outcomes and the type and frequency of the most used measures for each outcome is presented in Table 3. The number of measures used for each outcome varied widely. The mental health outcome of “PTSD,” categorized under Trauma and Stressor-Related Disorders, and the outcome “depression,” categorized under Depressive Disorders, had 22 and 15 measures respectively. Of the remaining outcome measures, 84% (157/188) had only one associated measure. The frequency distribution of unique measures across mental health categories by EWEs is summarized in Figure 4. A full list of mental health outcomes and measures (divided into primary and secondary sources) can be found in Supplementary Material 3.

4. Discussion

The main purpose of this scoping review was to map the currently available measures of mental health impact relevant to mental health outcomes that are directly influenced by EWEs. In turn, this supports the development of transparent and well-designed official statistics on climate change and health.[5] Mental health outcomes and measures found were abundant and diverse. We identified 188 unique mental health outcomes, of which PTSD, depression and anxiety were most commonly evaluated, and 130 unique measures of mental health impact. Currently the SOSCHI framework has one indicator on mental health: suicides attributable to extreme heat[10]. These results highlight that suicides are a small proportion of the mental health outcomes associated with EWEs. This review can help to inform the development and prioritisation of any future additional SOSCHI indicators. Flooding, extreme heat/heat waves and wildfires were the most frequently studied EWEs. LMICs were well represented, comprising just over half of the 29 countries.

Not surprisingly, there is a high heterogeneity in the measures of mental health impact used, highlighting an important opportunity for standardization. The variety of available measures has previously been identified in many contexts as a problem in determining the prevalence of mental health outcomes[11-13]. For example, in this review depression and PTSD were studied using 15 and 22 unique measures respectively, the majority of which were patient-reported questionnaires or screening tools. This heterogeneity makes it challenging to accurately quantify the breadth of the mental health burden associated with EWEs. In addition, the high use of

questionnaires/surveys can pose challenges for generating official statistics reports as it presents concerns about instrument validity and the representativeness (and generalisability) of the sample.[14] This is particularly noteworthy, as mental health outcomes are very difficult to measure without primary sources such as questionnaires and surveys. This was demonstrated in our results where most of the measures of mental health impact used were primary sources. However, for regular reporting of official statistics wide-scale population surveys are unrealistic. Accordingly, administrative data must be used for official statistics, but this too poses its own challenges on being representative of the true impacts.

It is also worth noting that some measures identified in this review, such as the Impact of Event Scale – Revised (IES-R) and PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5) tools, are intended to screen for symptoms of a mental health outcome (e.g., PTSD) but additional assessment is required to finalize the diagnosis[15]. Thus, care must be taken when interpreting reports as to whether the measure is being used to determine the prevalence of symptoms, or the prevalence of a diagnosed mental health condition. Establishing core outcomes and metrics for EWE impacts on mental health that support evidence synthesis and official statistics would improve consistency, support comparability and facilitate meta-analysis.

ICD codes were the most frequently used measure of mental health impact following EWEs. ICD codes are typically used in healthcare records and also in death certification. They differ in nature from primary sources such as rating scales in that ICD codes represent the endpoint of a diagnostic and classification process, to which one or more primary sources may have provided input along with clinical expertise. This scoping review identified the mental health ICD codes associated with EWEs, used to quantify 67 mental health outcomes. The ICD codes identified in this review provide decision makers with a comprehensive list of codes that can be used to track and report on mental health outcomes associated with EWEs. The frequent use of ICD codes supports decision-making needs, as they are easily operationalizable for national official statistics, provide a standardized way of reporting outcomes, and allow for comparisons over time.

However, ICD codes do not provide a panacea for mental health indicators relating to extreme weather events. Caution is needed in interpreting the most frequently reported ICD code categories as the most important mental health outcomes, as ease of measurement might drive their ubiquity, rather than actual mental health impact. It should be noted that the presence of ICD codes representing a long-term mental health condition or intellectual disability in a healthcare record does not necessarily suggest a causal relationship between the EWE and that condition but may rather reflect the vulnerability of individuals with a pre-existing diagnosis to the effects of the EWE exposure.

The accuracy of ICD codes is dependent on the expertise of the individual assigning the code, while diagnostic and classification practice may vary between countries and variability in coding has been observed across settings.[16 17] For example, stigma regarding mental health is variable by culture,[18] which may deter individuals from seeking care or reporting mental health concerns, leading to underreporting in certain regions. There is variability in classification definitions across ICD versions and health systems are slow to adopt newer versions. Finally, national-level ICD coded data is currently limited or unavailable in some countries.[19] Despite these challenges, ICD codes can be an effective tool to report and track health outcomes, particularly when paired with efforts to address some of the above limitations, such as policy and training to support more consistent implementation internationally.

Mental health outcomes related to specific EWEs also varied in abundance and diversity. All 11 EWEs identified evaluated a range of mental health outcomes, ranging in number from 64 mental health outcomes related to flooding to two mental health outcomes for snowstorms. The relationship between EWEs and multiple mental health outcomes from research spanning 29 unique countries is consistent with findings from numerous other studies showing that climate change is a major threat to global mental health.[8 20]

The extent of the impact of EWEs on mental health remains understudied. Our scoping review, in common with other recent work, found that there are still significant research gaps in the relationship of climate-sensitive EWEs and mental health outcomes.[20] However, it is challenging to interpret what these gaps mean, as absence of evidence cannot be assumed to represent an evidence of absence. More broadly, much work on the effectiveness of climate-mental health adaptations and projected future risks for mental health is needed, accompanying the development and dissemination of indicators to support decision-making.[8] This was highlighted in the recent UK Health Security Agency climate change and mental health report which called for additional research to understand the scale of climate change impact on mental health (particularly in vulnerable groups), active public health intervention and system-level changes to support long-term mental health impacts of climate change, and monitoring these impacts through indicators to raise awareness and drive policy change[21].

4.1 Strengths and limitations and how we mitigated them

This SOSCHI evidence synthesis has many strengths. The scoping review was rigorously carried out and designed in close collaboration between CPHTG and ONS; it was conducted according to a registered protocol and with the support of an experienced information specialist. In a pleasant contradistinction to much research on global health issues, LMICs are well represented in our sample.[22] Further, we

hope our data visualizations (Figure 3, Figure 4) allow end users (e.g., policy makers and researchers) to better extract insights from this rich data.

This scoping review also has several limitations. To support study feasibility, our eligibility criteria excluded publications prior to 2017, those only available in a language other than English and those reporting on indirect mental health outcomes from EWEs. Even with these limitations, we still had screened over 3,600 citations. The determination as to whether a mental health outcome was unique was limited by reported details in the included studies and entailed subjective assessments by the review team. To minimize this subjectivity, assessments were verified by a second reviewer during data abstraction. While the included studies reported mental health outcomes associated with EWEs, we cannot definitively attribute the EWEs to climate change. This is a universal challenge in climate change research. However, there is a growing body of evidence supporting the relationship between climate change and EWE frequency, duration and intensity[1] and recent transdisciplinary guidance documents on attribution of human health outcomes to climate change[23].

4.2 Directions for future research

We identified studies originating from 29 countries. LMICs are well represented in our sample, contributing diversity across national social, economic and climatic contexts.[22] This international representation is important to help map the impact of EWEs on mental health across regions, particularly since different parts of the world experience different types, frequency or intensity of EWEs. Future work to increase the availability of data on mental health outcomes across regions may also help to inform preventative population health and clinical strategies. For example, identifying countries or regions with a high occurrence of EWEs and where available data shows a low frequency of mental health outcome may help to uncover effective local or national policies, mental health systems and services that have allowed the country to be more climate change resilient when it comes to mental health.

5. Conclusions

SOSCHI is leveraging evidence synthesis for data-informed official statistics relevant to climate change and health. Indicators for how climate change impacts mental health must be based on recent and rigorous evidence synthesis, given that the amount of research in mental health and climate change is expanding rapidly. This scoping review contributes a global overview of current reporting practices and our findings support a need for standardization to enable global comparisons and decision-making. The SOSCHI project encompasses further work, building on our findings, via critical evaluation with policy end-users from low-, middle- and high-income countries; it is

anticipated that this engagement will improve the generalizability and utility of climate change mental health indicators across different international contexts.

6. Figure Legends

Figure 1. Study selection.

Figure 2. Frequency of reporting for each mental health outcome sorted into categories based on the groupings of diagnostic criteria and codes from the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5) and the International Classification of Diseases 10th and 11th revision.

Figure 3. Frequency of mental health outcomes by EWE.

EWEs definitions: Low pressure systems = Cyclone, hurricane, tornado, and typhoon; Extreme heat =Extreme heat/Heat waves; Extreme cold=Extreme cold/cold spells; Extreme precipitation = extreme rainfall, snowstorms.

Mental health definitions: NCD & NDD=Neurocognitive & neurodevelopmental disorders. Other mental health outcomes= general mental health outcomes, somatic symptom and related disorders, factors influencing health status or contact with health services.

Figure 4. Gap analysis of reported mental health outcomes and EWEs.

EWEs definitions: Low pressure systems = Cyclone, hurricane, tornado, and typhoon; Extreme heat =Extreme heat/Heat waves; Extreme cold=Extreme cold/cold spells; Extreme precipitation = extreme rainfall, snowstorms.

Mental health definitions: NCD & NDD=Neurocognitive & neurodevelopmental disorders. Other mental health outcomes= general mental health outcomes, somatic symptom and related disorders, factors influencing health status or contact with health services.

7. References

1. Otto F. *Angry Weather: Heat Waves, Floods, Storms, and the New Science of Climate Change*. Vancouver, Canada: Greystone Books, 2020.
2. Cissé G, McLeman R, Adams H, et al. Health, Wellbeing and the Changing Structure of Communities. *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability*, 2023:1041-170.
3. Frumkin H. Hope, Health, and the Climate Crisis. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health* 2022;5:100115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2022.100115>[published].

4. Thomson D, Cumpston M, Delgado-Figueroa N, et al. Protecting human health in a time of climate change: how Cochrane should respond. *Cochrane Database Systematic Reviews* 2022;3(3):Ed000156. 10.1002/14651858.Ed000156.
5. Office for National Statistics. Standards for official statistics on climate-health interactions. Secondary Office for National Statistics. Standards for official statistics on climate-health interactions. 2024.
<https://cy.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/programmesandprojects/standardsforofficialstatisticsonclimatehealthinteractions>.
6. Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* 2005;8(1):19-32. 10.1080/1364557032000119616.
10.1080/1364557032000119616</p>[published Online First: Epub Date]].
7. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med* 2018;169(7):467-73.10.7326/M18-0850
10.7326/M18-0850.
8. Aylward B, Cunsolo A, Vriezen R, Harper SL. Climate change is impacting mental health in North America: A systematic scoping review of the hazards, exposures, vulnerabilities, risks and responses. *International Review of Psychiatry* 2022;34(1):34-50. 10.1080/09540261.2022.2029368.
10.1080/09540261.2022.2029368</p>[published Online First: Epub Date]].
9. Wellcome. Low- and middle-income countries. Secondary Wellcome. Low- and middle-income countries. <https://wellcome.org/research-funding/guidance/prepare-to-apply/low-and-middle-income-countries>.
10. Pearce M WE, Glickman M, Lewis B, Ingole V. Standards for Official Statistics on Climate-Health Interactions (SOSCHI): Suicides attributed to extreme heat: methodology. Zenodo 2024
11. Karabegovic A, Indermaur E, Santi S, Fierz K. Prevalence of Psychiatric Symptoms and Mental Health Disorders in the Home Care Population: A Systematic Literature Review. *J Community Health Nurs* 2025:1-27. 10.1080/07370016.2025.2564069].
12. Borkenhagen D, Messier G, Masrani T, et al. Prevalence of Mental Health and Substance Use Disorders Among Adolescents Experiencing Homelessness: A Systematic Review. *Community Ment Health J* 2025. 10.1007/s10597-025-01492-7.

13. Caldarelli G, Pizzini B, Cosenza M, Troncone A. The prevalence of mental health conditions and effectiveness of psychological interventions among university students in Italy: A systematic literature review. *Psychiatry Res* 2024;342:116208. 10.1016/j.psychres.2024.116208|.
14. Pfeffermann D, Sverchkov M. Use of nonprobability samples for official statistics, state of the art. *Survey Methodology* 2025;50(1):169-96
15. American Psychological Association. PTSD Assessment Instruments. Secondary American Psychological Association. PTSD Assessment Instruments 2024. <https://www.apa.org/ptsd-guideline/assessment>.
16. Horsky J, Drucker EA, Ramelson HZ. Accuracy and Completeness of Clinical Coding Using ICD-10 for Ambulatory Visits. *AMIA Annu Symp Proc* 2018;16:912
17. Nelson S, Yin Y, Rivera E, et al. Are ICD codes reliable for observational studies? Assessing coding consistency for data quality. *DIGITAL HEALTH* 2024;10. 10.1177/20552076241297056.
18. Ahad A, Sanchez-Gonzalez M, Junquera P. Understanding and Addressing Mental Health Stigma Across Cultures for Improving Psychiatric Care: A Narrative Review. *Cureus* 2023;15:e39549. 10.7759/cureus.39549.
19. Otero Varela L, Knudsen S, Carpendale S, Eastwood C, Quan H. Comparing ICD-Data Across Countries: A Case for Visualization?, 2019.
20. Charlson F, Ali S, Augustinavicius J, et al. Global priorities for climate change and mental health research. *Environment International* 2022;158:106984. 10.1016/j.envint.2021.106984.
21. UK Health Security Agency. Climate change and mental health: thematic assessment report, 2025.
22. Woods WA, Watson M, Ranaweera S, Tajuria G, Sumathipala A. Under-representation of low and middle income countries (LMIC) in the research literature: Ethical issues arising from a survey of five leading medical journals: have the trends changed? *Global Public Health* 2023;18(1):2229890. 10.1080/17441692.2023.2229890
10.1080/17441692.2023.2229890.
23. Ebi KL, Haines A, Andrade RFS, et al. The attribution of human health outcomes to climate change: transdisciplinary practical guidance. *Climatic Change* 2025;178(8):143. 10.1007/s10584-025-03976-7.

Overview of the SOSCHI project

The impacts on health of rising temperatures, wildfires, extreme weather events and other direct and indirect effects of climate change are a major global concern. The most significant hazards and their impacts differ between countries and regions, as do the possibilities and priorities for climate change adaptation. National and local governments and other stakeholders need to have regular, reliable and comparable data to monitor climate impacts and inform adaptation strategies, based on a transparent and globally generalisable statistical framework. The SOSCHI project, led by the UK Office for National Statistics and funded by Wellcome, is developing a framework of indicators based on state-of-the-art statistical methods to measure climate-related health risks. To support global reporting and monitoring, we are also developing a knowledge-sharing platform, open-source tools, and R code. Our findings will also help highlight data gaps and help set the agenda for future improvement of data sources and methods.

Project partners

African Institute for Mathematical Sciences, Kigali, Rwanda

Cochrane Planetary Health Thematic Group, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada

Office for National Statistics, Newport, United Kingdom

Regional Institute for Population Studies, University of Ghana, Accra, Ghana

UK Health Security Agency, London, United Kingdom

United Nations Global Platform, New York, United States of America

The project is supported by Wellcome grant no. 224682/Z/21/Z